

HyDelta 4

WP3a – Defining gas quality tolerances in distribution grids and at network interfaces – Gas quality during grid coupling

D3a.1 Odorization policy for hydrogen distribution networks

Final version

Document summary

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Executive Summary

Odorisation is a proven safety measure in natural gas networks. By adding an odorant to naturally odourless natural gas, leaks can be detected quickly by the public. This HyDelta project has investigated the possible odorization options for the future Dutch hydrogen distribution network. The aim of the project is to provide guidance for network operators and, in particular, for policymakers who are responsible for developing policy and legislation for the new hydrogen distribution network. The starting point of the study is the current practice of odorization in the natural gas network, using THT as the odorant.

What are the differences between the hydrogen network and the natural gas network for odorization?

Hydrogen networks have characteristic differences compared to natural gas networks. These differences mean that a direct copy of the existing odorization practice for natural gas is not straightforward, and that a reconsideration of odorization in hydrogen distribution networks is necessary.

The Dutch **natural gas network** is built and managed largely top-down; the vast majority of supply takes place centrally from the national transmission network. Odorant injection (using THT) can therefore take place centrally high upstream in the system, at the entry of the regional transmission pipeline network (RTL). For decentrally produced green gas, odorization is a mandatory quality requirement. There is little to no gas produced decentrally at low pressure that is brought all the way back to the HTL. End use of the gas is primarily combustion-based.

In the **hydrogen network**, the expectation is that the system will be built bottom-up. Hydrogen production can occur both centrally and decentrally, including at locations further from national transmission pipelines. The initial system will be a connection between industrial clusters and local hydrogen networks. End use of the hydrogen is primarily as a feedstock and for combustion. The national transmission network will not be odorised.

Where is the best location for odorant injection in the network?

The location where odorization will take place in the hydrogen network is highly dependent on two factors: the future legislation and regulations surrounding odorization in hydrogen networks (which have not yet been established for hydrogen in the Dutch Energy Regulation (*Energieregeling*)), and the way in which the network will develop and structure itself. Depending on how these two aspects evolve, the following options can be chosen for odorization in hydrogen networks:

- A. **To odorise the entire hydrogen distribution network.** In practice, this represents a continuation of the current odorization policy. All end users who receive hydrogen at a pressure below 30 bar and are therefore not connected to the national transmission network, will receive hydrogen odorised with THT.
- B. **To odorise part of the hydrogen distribution network.** All infrastructure below a legally defined threshold pressure of x bar (for example, 8 bar) is odorised as standard with THT. Above this threshold pressure, odorization is optional and bespoke arrangements are made with regard to odorization and leak detection. The choice of whether or not to odorise depends on customer need, the volume of hydrogen production, and the required safety control measures with respect to leak detection.

With option A (see figure in Dutch summary), end users who do not want odorant will nonetheless receive odorised gas. Since Hynetwork (HTL) will not supply odorised gas, de-odorization will need to take place during boosting (feeding gas upstream) into the national hydrogen network. Odorisation will also need to take place at decentralised feed-in points in the DSO network.

With option B (see figure), the odorant obligation in legislation and regulations will need to be defined on the basis of pressure rather than network tier. The threshold pressure x will need to be determined carefully. Evidence will also need to be provided that not odorising parts of the gas distribution network from x to 16 bar is safe. HyDelta 4.0 work package D1C recommends not odorising industrial networks of intermediate pressure and suggests several operational and incident-preventing control measures to safely operate such networks.

A major advantage of option B is the complete absence of any need for de-odorization systems; odorant (sulphur-containing THT) does not need to be removed anywhere in the system. This option also better aligns with the process industry's need to receive unodorised gas (in tailored arrangements, 'maatwerk'). Option B therefore offers greater flexibility for varying needs per region, and more freedom for network operators to meet customer demand and the expectations of local authorities.

What are the current technologies for removing (de-odorizing) odorants from hydrogen?

For end-users connected to an odorised hydrogen network who do not want odorised gas because their production process cannot tolerate certain trace components in the odorant, a de-odorization requirement will arise. Adsorption is the most common technique for removing odorants from gases. Examples available on the market include fixed bed (packed column) processes and pressure swing adsorption (PSA) processes. The process technologies for purifying hydrogen from odorants are assessed as being at TRL 9 (technically and commercially ready). The adsorption material for the

selective removal of odorants (sulphur-containing and sulphur-free) from hydrogen is assessed at TRL 6–8 (demonstration phase), based on interviews.

An estimate has been made of the CAPEX for sulphur removal at gas flows of varying flow rates. This shows that PSA systems are more expensive to procure than fixed bed adsorption but are better suited to larger gas flows. Little could be said about the OPEX from an economic perspective, as the appropriate adsorption material is still under development. A rough estimate has been made of the adsorption material costs.

Is the option of not odorizing at all a feasible and sustainable solution?

Research is needed into not odorizing networks above 8 bar, and what control measures ('maatwerk') would then be required. Previous HyDelta work packages have stated that not odorizing below 8 bar could increase safety risks. However, above 8 bar there is a possibility that it may be safe in some locations with the correct control measures.

Is the use of sulfur-free odorants a feasible and sustainable solution?

Sulfur-free odorants must align with the needs of hydrogen end users. This means they will need to be tested for interaction with industrial catalysts. Testing has been conducted for interaction with fuel cells (platinum), but this group of end users is expected to be minimal, as they will be supplied by tube trailers or specially designed networks. It will also need to be investigated whether the introduction of sulfur-free odorants into the national hydrogen network is permitted by Hynetwork. This will need to be done in consultation with Hynetwork, and consideration will need to be given to the needs of end users of the national hydrogen network and requirements of neighboring countries. If a sulfur-free odorant exists that meets all requirements following the above investigations, then Option A, as described in the report, would be a suitable option for odorization policy.

Nederlandse samenvatting

Odorisatie is een bewezen veiligheidsmaatregel in aardgasnetwerken. Door het toevoegen van een geurstof aan het van nature geurloze aardgas worden lekkages door omstanders snel waargenomen. Dit HyDelta-project heeft de mogelijke odorisatie opties in het toekomstige Nederlandse waterstofdistributienetwerk onderzocht. Het doel van dit project is om handvaten te bieden aan netwerkbeheerders maar vooral ook beleidsmakers die aan de basis staan van beleid en wetgeving over het nieuwe waterstofdistributienetwerk. Vertrekpunt is de huidige praktijk van odorisatie in het aardgasnetwerk met THT (tetrahydrothiopheen) als odorant.

Wat zijn de verschillen tussen het waterstofnetwerk en het aardgasnetwerk met betrekking tot odorisatie?

Waterstofnetwerken hebben kenmerkende verschillen ten opzichte van aardgasnetwerken. Deze verschillen maken dat een directe kopie van de bestaande odorisatiepraktijk voor aardgas niet vanzelfsprekend is en dat een heroverweging van odorisatie in waterstofdistributienetwerken noodzakelijk is.

Het Nederlandse aardgasnetwerk is grotendeels *top-down* opgebouwd en beheerd, het overgrote deel van de levering vindt centraal plaats vanuit het landelijke transportnetwerk. Odorantinjectie (met THT) kan hierdoor hoog in het systeem centraal plaatsvinden in Regionaal TransportLeidingnet (RTL). Voor decentraal geproduceerd groengas is odorisatie daarbij een verplichte kwaliteitseis. Er is in het aardgasnetwerk weinig tot geen sprake van gas wat op lage druk decentraal geproduceerd wordt en helemaal teruggebracht wordt naar het HTL. Eindgebruik van het aardgas in RTL en distributienet is voornamelijk op basis van verbranding.

Het is de verwachting dat in het waterstofnetwerk meer *bottom-up* opgebouwd gaat worden. Productie van waterstof kan zowel centraal en decentraal gebeuren, ook op locaties verder weg van landelijke transportleidingen. Het initiële systeem zal een verbinding zijn tussen industriële clusters en lokale waterstofnetwerken. Eindgebruik van de waterstof is voornamelijk op basis van grondstof en verbranding, met mogelijk mobiliteit. Het landelijke transportnetwerk zal niet geodoriseerd worden.

Waar kan odorant-injectie in het waterstofnetwerk het beste plaatsvinden in het netwerk?

De locatie waar geodoriseerd gaat worden in het waterstofnetwerk is sterk afhankelijk van twee factoren: de toekomstige wet- en regelgeving rondom odorisatie in waterstofnetwerken (die voor waterstof nog niet is vastgesteld in de *Energierегeling*), en de wijze waarop het netwerk zich zal ontwikkelen en structureren. Afhankelijk hoe deze twee aspecten zich ontwikkelen, kan voor odorisatie in waterstofnetwerken gekozen worden om:

- A. **Het gehele waterstofdistributienet te odoriseren.** In feite is dit het doorzetten van het huidige odorisatiebeleid. Alle eindgebruikers die waterstof willen ontvangen op een druk lager dan 30 bar - en dus niet aangesloten zijn op het landelijke transport netwerk - ontvangen met THT geodoriseerd waterstof.
- B. **Een deel van het waterstofdistributienet te odoriseren.** Alle infrastructuur onder een wettelijk bepaalde grensdruk van x bar (bijvoorbeeld 8 bar) wordt standaard geodoriseerd met THT. Boven deze grensdruk wordt optioneel geodoriseerd en maatwerk geleverd met betrekking tot odorisatie en lekdetectie. De keuze om wel of niet te odoriseren is afhankelijk van de klantbehoefte, de hoeveelheid waterstofproductie en de benodigde veiligheidsbeheersmaatregelen met betrekking tot lekdetectie.

Bij optie A (zie figuur) ontvangen eindgebruikers die geen odorant willen toch geodoriseerd gas. Omdat Hynetwork (HTL) geen geodoriseerd gas gaat leveren, zal er de-odorisatie moeten plaatsvinden bij het boosten (terugleveren) naar de het landelijk waterstofnetwerk. Ook zal er odorisatie plaats moeten vinden bij decentrale invoeders in het DSB-net (distributiesysteembeheerder).

Bij optie B (zie figuur) zal de odorantverplichting zoals die nu in wet- en regelgeving is vastgelegd moeten worden gedefinieerd op basis van druk in plaats van netvlak. De grensdruk x zal zorgvuldig moeten worden bepaald. Ook zal er bewijs moeten worden geleverd dat het niet-odoriseren van delen van het gasdistributienetten van x tot 16 bar veilig is. HyDelta 4.0 werkpakket WP1C adviseert dat odorisatie ongewenst is voor industriële netwerken met middelhoge drukken. Dit werkpakket stelt ook beheersmaatregelen voor om ongeodoriseerde delen van het waterstofnetwerk veilig te realiseren.

Een groot voordeel van optie B is de volledige afwezigheid van de behoefte naar de-odorisatie-systemen; nergens in het systeem hoeft odorant (zwavelhoudend THT) te worden verwijderd. Ook sluit deze optie beter aan bij de behoefte van de procesindustrie om ongeodoriseerd gas te ontvangen ('maatwerk'). Optie B biedt daarmee meer flexibiliteit voor wisselende behoeften per regio, en meer vrijheid voor netbeheerders om te voldoen aan de klantvraag en verwachtingen van lokale bestuurders.

Wat zijn de huidige technologieën voor het verwijderen (de-odorisatie) van odoranten uit waterstof?

Voor afnemers die aangesloten zijn op een geodoriseerd waterstofnetwerk maar dat niet willen omdat hun productieproces niet tegen bepaalde sporencomponenten in de odorant kan, zal een de-odorisatievraag ontstaan. Adsorptie is de meest voorkomende techniek voor het verwijderen van odoranten uit gassen. Op de markt zijn voorbeelden van *fixed bed* (*packed column*) processen en *pressure-swing* adsorptieprocessen (PSA). De procestechnieken om waterstof te zuiveren van odoranten wordt beoordeeld als zijnde TRL 9 (technisch en commercieel gereed). Het adsorptiemateriaal voor de selectieve verwijdering van odoranten (zwavelhoudend en zwavelvrij) uit waterstof wordt beoordeeld met TRL 6-8 (demonstratie fase).

Er is een inschatting gemaakt van de CAPEX van zwavelverwijdering bij gasstromen van verschillende debieten. Daaruit blijkt dat PSA-systemen in aanschaf duurder zijn dan *fixed-bed* adsorptie, maar wel beter geschikt zijn voor grotere gasstromen. Over de OPEX kon weinig gezegd worden op economisch gebied, aangezien het juiste adsorptiemateriaal nog in ontwikkeling is. Er is een grove inschatting gemaakt van de adsorptiemateriaalkosten.

Is de optie om helemaal niet te odoriseren, een haalbare en houdbare oplossing?

Nader onderzoek is nodig naar het niet-odoriseren van waterstofnetten boven 8 bar en de daarbij vereiste beheersmaatregelen. In eerdere HyDelta-werkpakketten is vastgesteld dat het achterwege laten van odorisatie onder de 8 bar kan leiden tot een toename van veiligheidsrisico's.¹ Voor netten boven de 8 bar bestaat echter de mogelijkheid dat het in specifieke situaties en op bepaalde locaties veilig kan zijn om zonder odorisatie te opereren, mits passende aanvullende veiligheidsmaatregelen worden getroffen.

Is het gebruik van zwavelvrije odorant een haalbare en houdbare oplossing?

Zwavelvrije odoranten bieden mogelijk een oplossing, met name voor optie A. Zwavelvrije odoranten dienen aan te sluiten bij de behoeften van eindgebruikers van waterstof (zie onderstaand figuur). Dit betekent dat deze stoffen zullen moeten worden getest op mogelijke interactie met industriële katalysatoren. Uit de literatuur blijkt dat al onderzoek is gedaan naar interactie met brandstofcellen (met name platinum). Deze groep eindgebruikers zal echter naar verwachting minimaal zijn, aangezien deze belevend zullen worden door tube trailers of speciaal daarvoor aangelegde waterstofnetten.

¹ Zie ook HyDelta 4 D1c.1 rondom veiligheidskaders

Daarnaast zal in overleg met Hynetwork moeten worden onderzocht of de invoer van zwavelvrije odoranten in het landelijke waterstofnet is toegestaan. Ook dient aandacht te worden besteed aan de behoeften van eindgebruikers van het landelijke waterstofnet en aan de afstemming met aansluitingen op netten in buurlanden. Als er een zwavelvrije odorant bestaat die na bovenstaande onderzoeken voldoet aan alle eisen, dan zou Optie A, zoals hierboven beschreven, een geschikte optie zijn voor het odorisatiebeleid, omdat er dan niet gedeodoriseerd hoeft te worden.

Introduction

Hydrogen distribution is on the verge of large-scale deployment. In the coming decade, it is expected that producers, storage operators, and end users will be interconnected via a network of repurposed and newly constructed transmission and distribution pipelines. As with natural gas, it is essential to establish a quality specification for hydrogen at an early stage. A good specification limits contaminants in the transported gas, ensuring that hydrogen arrives at the end user at a consistent quality and that the integrity of the network and storage facilities is maintained. Work package WP3b investigates this safety and quality assurance.

Historically, odorization has been one of the most important elements for the safety of end users and bystanders in natural gas networks. Odorisation involves adding a characteristic odour to odourless natural gas by means of an odorant. If a leak occurs in a section of the network where odorant has been added, people in the vicinity are alerted by the smell. Most Dutch people instinctively recognise the sulphurous (rotten egg) smell of the odorant as coming from a gas leak and can therefore take action to prevent damage or danger. The smell of the odorant has become synonymous with what is colloquially called 'gas', without people explicitly knowing that natural gas itself has no odour.

It would be logical and advantageous from a policy perspective to continue the current odorization practices used for natural gas in the future hydrogen network. This would preserve the warning function in the event of a leak. However, there are important differences between public² natural gas networks and public hydrogen networks:

- **The tolerance of end-user equipment for odorants in the gas they receive differs for hydrogen compared to natural gas.**
 - Industrial feedstock and fuel cell hydrogen users cannot tolerate (sulphur-containing) odorants.
- **The initial hydrogen network is also expected to be developed bottom-up** (regionally, in clusters, decentralised demand-driven expansion) compared with the top-down natural gas network. Gasunie, (the transmission system operator (TSB)), transports gas through the HTL (high-pressure transmission pipeline network), which is distributed geographically to regional transmission and distribution networks at progressively lower pressures.
 - The initial national hydrogen network will most likely consist of major transport lines connecting industrial clusters, regional networks, and local distribution networks. There will also be standalone networks that are not (yet initially) connected to the national hydrogen network.
 - Odorisation in the natural gas network currently takes place after the HTL - and at green gas feed-in points - this need not be the case for the hydrogen network.
- **End-user demand and production volumes for hydrogen are likely to be more variable and more decentralised.**
 - Hydrogen production may be linked to local excesses in solar or wind power. End use will be less seasonal because domestic hydrogen use will initially be lower and because hydrogen as a feedstock will represent a major source of demand. Natural gas use is more seasonal since heating for houses/businesses in winter is a major end-use.
 - Feed-in of locally produced hydrogen will occur more frequently at a regional level, which may cause regional networks to become overloaded. This can create a need

² Private hydrogen or natural gas networks are not always odorized. In these networks alternative leak detection methods – such as continuous monitoring techniques – are commonly employed.

for reverse flow (boosting) from regional networks to the main transmission network.

This HyDelta project investigates odorization and possible de-odorization options for the future hydrogen distribution network and considers the abovementioned differences between hydrogen and natural gas infrastructure. The aim of the project is to provide guidance for network operators and, in particular, for policymakers who are responsible for the foundations of policy and legislation on the new hydrogen network. The research questions (*research questions*, RQ) are as follows:

RQ 1: What are the differences between the hydrogen network and the natural gas network with regard to odorization?

RQ 2: Where is the best location for odorant injection in the network?

RQ 3: What are the current technologies for removing (de-odorising) odorants from hydrogen?

RQ 4: Is not odorising parts of the network, or the use of sulphur-free odorants, a feasible and sustainable solution?

1 RQ1: What are the differences between the hydrogen network and the natural gas network with regard to odorization?

1.1 The natural gas network and odorization

Figuur 1 provides a simplified overview of the current Dutch natural gas network and how odorization takes place within it. The figure can largely be read *top-down*. Gas is transported centrally through the HTL by transmission system operator (TSB) Gasunie. Branches from the HTL at lower pressure form the regional transmission pipeline network (RTL). Further distribution is done by distribution system operators (DSB) at lower pressures (Enexis, Stedin, Liander, etc.). Gas flows predominantly downwards in the figure, where the network has progressively lower pressures and is topologically more decentralised and meshed. Figuur 2 shows how this leads to a branched structure. The parts outlined in red in this figure are odorised.

Figuur 1: Simplified, schematic topology of the natural gas network in the Netherlands. Note that terminology in Dutch may differ, and the terms used here are for reference only. Red outlined blocks indicate that the network is odorized.

Figuur 2: Structure of the natural gas network. Orange triangles are M&R stations, green dots are GOS. Source: Gasunie.

Odorisation is legally required in the network for natural gas networks through the *Energierегeling*³ from the distribution system operators onwards, at the interface between Gasunie and the interface between Gasunie and the distribution network managed by the DSB. In practice, odorization mostly occurs⁴ at *meet- en regelstations*⁵ (M&R stations, the orange triangles in Figuur 2), of which there are approximately 90 in the Netherlands. M&R stations are located at the interface between the HTL and Gasunie's regional transmission network (RTL, 16–40 bar). The handover point between the TSB and the DSB is at the gas receiving stations at the end of the RTL. This means odorization occurs a significant upstream distance before handover of the gas from TSB to DSB. All networks and end-users *downstream* of the M&R stations therefore receive odorised gas from the RTL.

There are two important exceptions to this rule. Green gas is produced decentrally by companies that ferment biomass into biogas and upgrade it to green gas that may be fed into the network. As discussed above, odorization is one of the quality requirements in the distribution network. Green gas is therefore odorised and boosted up to transport pressure by *booster stations*. Examples of green gas producers include farmers who ferment manure or vegetable waste, as well as producers on a larger scale who, for example, convert industrial food waste like beet pulp into biogas. Some parts of the network – such as is the case in Flevoland – are not odorized at M&R stations but elsewhere. (Gasunie Transport Services, 2025).

The odorant used in the Dutch natural gas network is tetrahydrothiophene (THT). This is a sulphur-containing liquid that, at the correct concentration in natural gas, produces the familiar Dutch 'gas smell'. The requirements laid down in the *Energierегeling* (formerly: *Regeling gaskwaliteit*) for the THT concentration are 10–40 mg/m³ (n). A nominal concentration is 18–20 mg/m³ THT, approximately 5 ppm (v).

In *Bijlage 1* of the *Energierегeling* it is indicated that natural gas at feed-in should comply to the following standard (Dutch, for literal reference):

³ Energy directive.

⁴ Note that some GOS also include odorization systems.

⁵ Metrology and control stations.

THT-gehalte* (odorant)	in HTL: reukloos gas	0	mg THT/m ³ (n)
	in RTL: ruikbaar gas	10 – 40	mg THT/m ³ (n)
	in DSB-net: ruikbaar gas	10 – 40	mg THT/m ³ (n)

* THT mag worden vervangen door een stof met een vergelijkbare alarmerende werking.

Translated to English:

THT-concentration* (odorant)	in HTL: unodorized gas	0	mg THT/m ³ (n)
	in RTL: odorized gas	10 – 40	mg THT/m ³ (n)
	in DSB-net: odorized gas	10 – 40	mg THT/m ³ (n)

* THT may be replaced with a substance with equal leak-indicating properties/comparable alerting effect.

A comparable THT requirement applies to the H-gas (high-calorific natural gas) and G-gas (Groningen gas) network. The note on a *comparable alerting effect* applies to G-gas. The general guideline states that “*The alerting effect of odorised gas must be adequate at all times*”. The *Energiereregeling* therefore allows for the choice of an alternative odorant as long as the gas is adequately odorised and provides an option for odorising or not odorising the RTL. Odorisation is explicitly required in the gas distribution system however, and the operator of this network is a legal entity designated as the owner of that network by the Minister for Climate and Green Growth in Article 1 of the *Energiewet*. This operator is the DSO (Enexis, Liander, Stedin etc.).

In structural terms, the natural gas network is organised around a centralised⁶ top-down structure characterised by a progressively more decentralised structure and lower pressure as one moves closer to the small end user. This means that central, high-capacity, high-pressure pipelines supply regional, smaller pipelines at lower pressure but greater in number, which in turn supply local low-pressure pipelines. In a top-down system, it is therefore economically advantageous to odorise at approximately 80 M&R stations in the network, before the gas is distributed. Any gas below the M&R-level is odorised. If odorization were to take place at gas receiving stations (GOS), more than 900 odorization systems would need to be installed, which is economically inefficient.

⁶ Central in this context means a large transport capacity on one or a few lines, where decentralised means transport capacity geographically distributed over multiple branches.

Figur 3: Overview of natural gas network end users in 2024. Source: CBS (Statistics Netherlands, 2026).

End users of natural gas from the network consist of industry (38%), power generation (23%), the built environment (29%), and the agricultural sector (11%). A large share of industrial use is energy-related (burning natural gas in boilers for heat/steam generation, and direct burners for, for example, glass and brick production). The remainder is industry in which natural gas - principally the methane/ethane in the natural gas - is used as a feedstock in the production of plastics and other fuels (such as hydrogen) and in refining. Relevant to the odorization question is that it is primarily this latter sector that is sensitive to sulphur-containing odorants. Several industrial processes that use catalysts are sensitive to sulphur components, as these can deactivate the catalysts. These industries receive gas from the unodorised, high-pressure part of the network. In the low-pressure part of the network, there are few end users who are sensitive to odorants.

In summary, the main characteristics of the natural gas network with regard to odorization are:

- Natural gas is transported and distributed *top-down* top-down from the HTL to increasingly decentralised and lower-pressure networks.
- Odorisation is used as a safety measure. The smell of the gas has an alerting function in the event of a gas leak.
- By law, natural gas must be odorised when it is in the DSO network.
- Natural gas is odorised with sulphur-containing THT.
- Odorisation takes place at approximately 80-90 M&R stations and some GOS under Gasunie's responsibility, distributed across the Netherlands. Networks at pressures below this point therefore contain odorised gas.
- Odorisation also takes place at green gas feed-in points (decentralised production).
- End users of the natural gas network are industries, businesses, and households.
- End users who are sensitive to odorants generally offtake gas from the HTL at high pressure.

- End users of the odorised part of the network, predominantly end users who use natural gas for combustion (heating), are generally not sensitive to odorants.

1.2 The hydrogen network and odorization

There is still some uncertainty about the structure of the future hydrogen network. This also gives rise to considerable policy uncertainty, including with regard to odorization of the hydrogen network. Figuur 4 shows what is currently known about the hydrogen network in the Netherlands, in the same framework as shown above in Figuur 1. Hynetwork, a subsidiary of Gasunie, has been designated as the transmission system operator for the hydrogen network. Hynetwork is preparing existing pipelines for repurposing and is laying new hydrogen pipelines.

Figuur 4: Simplified overview of the current **known** parts of the future hydrogen network.

The national hydrogen network (Hynetwork) will operate at a pressure of 30–50 bar(g), with a design pressure of 66.2 bar(g). EZK has also established an indicative quality specification: the “*Indicative quality and temperature specification for Hydrogen Network Netherlands*”. This specification includes no odorant level (Hynetwork, 2024b), and it is therefore assumed that, as with the current HTL, the network will be entirely unodorised. It is known that the operational industrial hydrogen networks of, among others, Air Liquide, are not odorized in practice (900 km, <80 bar) (Kiwa Technology, 2022).

There are also changing responsibilities in the hydrogen network compared with the natural gas network. Hynetwork explicitly states that connecting small businesses and homes is **not** its responsibility:

“No, we will not connect your home to the hydrogen network. (...) Connecting homes and smaller businesses is the job of regional grid operators, such as Stedin or Enexis. They are exploring the possibility of a hydrogen network for homes and smaller businesses in the future.”

This means that Hynetwork’s responsibility ends below 30 bar, where the current interface between the TSB (Gasunie) and the DSB is at a maximum of 16 bar (in practice 8 bar). This creates uncertainty about who is responsible for odorization below 30 bar, if required. In the natural gas network, this takes place within Gasunie’s network; in the hydrogen network, Hynetwork delivers unodorised gas up to a minimum of 30 bar.

Figuur 5: Structure of the proposed hydrogen network. Source: Hynetwork.

Figuur 5 shows the proposed structure for the national high-pressure hydrogen network. A large part of the network involves repurposing existing pipelines, and therefore broadly follows the route of the current natural gas HTL. The initial network is a connection between large industrial clusters in the Netherlands, storage facilities, international connections, and import and production sites (Hynetwork, 2024a).

Building the network from connections between industrial clusters and local distribution networks gives the hydrogen network a different structure from the natural gas network. The hydrogen network is primarily demand-driven (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2024) and *bottom-up*. Furthermore, rather than central-to-decentralised distribution, the pattern is more one of clustering around large industrial clusters and local hydrogen initiatives.

There is also an expectation (certainly in the early years) that hydrogen production will be more local than central (compared to natural gas), and that during periods of overproduction there will be limited local storage capacity. The development of local networks will take place before Hynetwork is fully operational, meaning that at least some development occurs *bottom-up*. This will likely create a need for more decentralised reverse flow from distribution and regional networks to the Hynetwork, as more storage capacity exists in the Hynetwork (and hydrogen storage) than locally. With regard to odorization, this has the following implications:

- Hynetwork supplies unodorised hydrogen to its customers/connected parties in the large industrial clusters (or regional networks).
- Whether odorization is desired may vary per consumer/customer/cluster, depending on the local built environment, the pressure levels, and which end users are connected to the cluster.
- Any hydrogen production, storage, or import facilities in the cluster/regional network will need to feed separately into the national hydrogen network, or a de-odorization/booster station will need to be installed if this facility is connected to an odorised local network. No de-odorization system is required for an unodorized cluster.

The changes compared with the natural gas network are not only structural. The end users of the hydrogen network also differ from those of the natural gas network. A stakeholder study conducted for the European Commission in 2025 (European Commission – Directorate-General for Energy, 2025) found that the largest initial demand for hydrogen comes from industries that already use hydrogen as a feedstock. The ammonia industry (Haber–Bosch process) and the fuels industry (refining and Fischer–Tropsch process) lead the way. This is followed by demand from the steel industry, the high-energy industry, and finally the power generation sector.

In the Netherlands, the first HyRegions report (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2024) established that end users of hydrogen as a feedstock have a higher willingness to pay, but that there is also demand for heat production (energy-intensive industry) from the hydrogen network. Both reports indicate that demand for mobility applications (fuel cells and combustion for transport) is limited and uncertain. Both reports also establish that demand for hydrogen from the built environment (especially domestic use) will be limited, whereas for natural gas this represents a significant share of demand. Finally, the price of hydrogen is calculated differently to that of natural gas: on the basis of purity rather than calorific value.

HyDelta 1.0: D2.2 (Vlap, 2021) investigated which end users of the hydrogen network could be affected by sulphur-containing odorants such as THT. That report established that no problems are expected with domestic and commercial combustion equipment and THT, and that the only knowledge gap in this area is turbines for power generation, as hydrogen turbines are not yet fully developed. Fuel cells are sensitive to odorants, but as described in the paragraph above, the initial demand from the network for fuel cells is low. The most important finding of the report is the confirmation that odorant will need to be removed for specific feedstock processes in the chemical industry. However, it is also concluded that almost all feedstock processes will be connected to the Hynetwork (due to the high capacity required) and will therefore by definition use unodorised hydrogen gas from the high-pressure network.

The HyRegions 2 report (Netbeheer Nederland, 2024) endorses the role of regional network operators in providing gas infrastructure outside the industrial concentration areas identified in the first HyRegions report. For these industries, which may be located near the built environment, flood defences, and other obstacles, it may be technically impossible or economically challenging to connect directly to high-pressure pipelines. Low-pressure networks can often be constructed in such regions. Regional network operators could also connect industries not located near the main Hynetwork pipelines to the hydrogen network. Finally, the report also establishes that low-pressure networks are in some cases more cost-efficient and meet customer needs.

With regard to the odorization of DSO hydrogen networks, there is still complete uncertainty about how the legal obligation for odorization will be defined. The *Energiereregeling* is clear about the mandatory odorization in DSO networks, but these laws are specifically aimed at natural gas infrastructure distributing L, G, or H-gas. As a result, the legal obligation for odorization of hydrogen DSO networks has not yet been defined and remains open to interpretation. The *Energiereregeling* for natural gas allows for the choice of an alternative odorant as long as the gas is adequately odorised. No odorant has yet been specified for the hydrogen network, but the expectation is that here too the choice will be kept open for alternative odorants, with a view to the needs of end users.

In HyDelta 1.0 WPD2.4 (E. Polman, 2022) it was established that from a safety perspective there are risks associated with not odorising hydrogen networks below 8 bar. It is therefore plausible that in the built environment there will be a need for odorization to guarantee the safety of distribution.

However, given the structure of the hydrogen network, it is also plausible that large parts will not need to be odorised, as the initial demand will come primarily from industry. In a survey as part of HyRegions 2, 75% of industries indicated a pressure requirement below 16 bar. Whether this pressure requirement fell above 8 bar was not reported (Netbeheer Nederland, 2024).

In summary, the main characteristics of the hydrogen network with regard to odorization are:

- Hynetwork is responsible for the national hydrogen network from 30 bar to approximately 66 bar. Hynetwork will not odorise the hydrogen it supplies.
- Structurally, the hydrogen network differs from the natural gas network. Bottom-up initiatives determine connections, and there will be decentralised and clustered production and offtake.
- It is not yet clear who is permitted to construct and manage the regional hydrogen networks.
- There is a high degree of uncertainty about the responsibilities for odorization and the general policy for hydrogen infrastructure below 30 bar. However, according to the HyRegions reports, there is a need for hydrogen infrastructure below 30–16 bar.
- The hydrogen network has a different mix of end users than the natural gas network, which will likely result in different requirements with regard to odorization.
- There is uncertainty about the odorization obligation for hydrogen networks. There is, however, an increased safety risk when odorization is not applied at distribution below 8 bar.
- Feedstock end users are sensitive to THT, but these large-scale industries will primarily connect to the national hydrogen network. However, some feedstock end users are also seeking connections in regional networks.

1.3 Overview of differences between the natural gas network and the hydrogen network

Tabel 1: Overview of relevant differences between the natural gas network and the hydrogen network with regard to odorization.

Property	Natural gas network	Hydrogen network
Structure	Top-down network in which the system becomes more decentralised at lower pressures.	More bottom-up, demand-driven network in which the high-pressure pipelines connect clusters.
End users	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Industry (38%) 2. Built environment (29%) 3. Power generation (23%) 4. Agricultural sector (11%) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Industry <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. As feedstock b. For heat 2. Power generation <p>Later: possibly on a smaller scale built environment, mobility, etc.</p>
Sensitivity of end users to sulphur-containing odorant	Yes, feedstock industry.	Yes, feedstock industry and mobility. Power generation still unknown.
Production	Central production and storage connected to Hynetwork. Green gas production at lower pressure with boosters to the regional network or Hynetwork.	Production and import to Hynetwork and decentralised and variable production and import. Boosters to Hynetwork for storage and transport.
Legal odorization obligation?	Yes, established in gas legislation at handover to DSO.	Not yet determined.
Odorant choice	THT, but alternatives permitted.	Not yet determined, but alternatives may be permitted.
Odorisation location	M&R stations, at Hynetwork/RTL interface ~<40 bar. Green gas feed-in points ~4–8 bar.	Not yet determined.

2 RQ2: Where is the best location for odorant injection in the network?

This chapter investigates where odorant is best injected in the hydrogen network, based on the known information described above about the future transmission and distribution network for hydrogen. For this chapter, it is assumed that the gas is odorised with THT at 18 mg/m³ (n) nominal (10–40 mg/m³ (n) legally) as established in Annex 1 (*Bijlage 1*) of the *Energieregeling*. It is also assumed that there is an odorization obligation, and that Hynetwork will not odorise within its own network or at the exit point. Two basic variants for odorization are proposed and will be weighed against each other.

2.1 Option A: Odorising the entire distribution network (<16 bar)

Figuur 6: Overview of the proposed Option A for odorization. Parts of the network outlined in red are odorised; parts outlined in blue are unodorized.

The first proposed option, Option A, is a continuation of the current odorization policy for natural gas networks. In this design, odorization (with THT) can take place directly after exit from the national network. No definitive decision has yet been taken on who will odorise, but there are several options - for example, the DSB itself or the TSB acting on behalf of the DSB. In any case, a limited number of injection points will be required (compared with variant B) across the entire network, and all gas *downstream* of the national hydrogen network will be odorised. This increases the safety of distribution infrastructure by ensuring that any leak in the DSB network would be sufficiently detectable by smell.

A further advantage is that this design complies with one interpretation of the current *Energieregeling* and the *Energiewet* as odorization takes place before the TSB/DSB interface. As a result, few legislative changes will be needed - only the addition of a hydrogen gas specification to the *Energieregeling*.

The main disadvantage of this design is that de-odorization will need to take place at every point of feed-in from the DSO network to the national hydrogen network. If no bypass is constructed, a producer operating at 4 bars (such as an electrolyser) will first need to odorize before injection into the DSO network, and this same gas will subsequently need to be de-odorized when fed into the Hynetwork. This wastes odorant and adsorption material and results in a loss of (cost) efficiency throughout the entire system. All industries that do not receive hydrogen directly from the Hynetwork will receive odorised gas, and those few that use hydrogen as a feedstock or in a fuel cell will need to de-odorise.

2.2 Option B: Only partially odorizing the network

Figuur 7: Overview of the proposed Option B for odorization. Parts of the network outlined in red are odorised; parts outlined in blue are unodorized. The dashed line marked 'threshold pressure x' indicates the legal obligation for odorization.

Option B addresses the changing requirements for odorization of hydrogen end users compared with natural gas end users and offers flexibility for local variation in network requirements. In this design, the DSB section of the network is divided into two layers:

- A layer from x to 16 bar where odorization is **optional**.
- A layer below threshold pressure x bar where odorization is **legally required**.

The lower layer consists of local domestic and commercial networks in the built environment, connected below the threshold pressure of x bar. Based on the findings from HyDelta - which show that the safety risk increases when odorization is not applied below 4–8 bar (E. Polman, 2022) - it is plausible that a legal obligation will be introduced to odorise these hydrogen networks. For these networks, in Option B there is **no** reverse flow to higher-pressure networks permitted. Where this pressure point lies has not yet been established and is therefore referred to as x bar.

In the middle layer – above x bar and below the national hydrogen network - regional networks/industrial clusters can be connected to the regional hydrogen network. As clear legislation does not yet exist, and this part of the network is developing *bottom-up*, Option B allows here for **tailored solutions (maatwerk)** with regard to odorization, and for these networks odorization is optional. However, a deliberate assessment must be made for each regional network as to whether or not it will be odorised. If no odorization takes place, free reverse flow to the national hydrogen network is permitted. This is not permitted if odorization takes place.

Figuur 8 presents three pillars that contribute to the decision-making process regarding whether a regional network or industrial cluster should or should not be odorized. In collaboration with the EAG (Expert Assessment Group), the pillars have been defined as:

Figuur 8: Three pillars that can contribute to decision-making regarding the odorization of regional networks.

External safety. This pillar indicates how the surroundings of the network determine the safety question and thereby the choice of whether or not to odorise. The greater the safety need regarding leaks, the stronger the preference for an odorized network.

Example: *A regional network in the Maasvlakte area could use alternative methods of leak detection (e.g. continuous monitoring, ultrasonic leak detection) as odorization is less effective in a sparsely populated area and the risk of damage is lower. On the other hand, for a pipeline/network through a residential area in Deventer, odour recognition of the gas is important.*

Proportion of end users sensitive to odorant. This pillar indicates how many connected end users are sensitive to certain trace components in the odorant.

Example: *In a regional network with many sustainable aviation fuel producers that use catalysts in their production process, odorization is not efficient, as all these off takers would need to purify the gas themselves. For a network supplying ovens and boilers, an elevated sulphur level has little to no impact, as the odorant burns harmlessly.*

Production volume. This pillar indicates whether a large or small volume of hydrogen is produced or imported in the regional network.

Example: *If there is a large import terminal where hydrogen is delivered by ship, this gas will need to be odorized where required, even for infrequent deliveries. For an unodorized network, the gas can be injected directly into the national hydrogen network without additional steps.*

When a new network/cluster above x bar is being designed, or when an existing hydrogen network is being connected, a decision can be made on the basis of the pillars as to whether odorization is required. This design provides scope for network operators to deliver tailored solutions (*maatwerk*) that meet the needs of end users, other local networks, producers, and local authorities. By offering *maatwerk*, it is likely that this will strengthen the development of regional networks.

However, Option B does require a different legislative approach to odorization than the current one for natural gas. As discussed above, the *Energiereregeling* stipulates that gas in regional networks must be odorized (detectable by smell). This implies that odorization must take place before delivery to the distribution network, meaning that in practice it is implemented at the TSB/DSB interface or further upstream. If Option B were to be chosen as the basis for hydrogen infrastructure, a legal

obligation will need to be included for odorization below x bar. For unodorized regional networks, scope could be provided to use alternative control measures other than odorization.

Finally, the choice of Option B requires the determination of the threshold pressure x below which odorization becomes mandatory. This must be done on the basis of safety considerations, but it is recommended that the following considerations are also taken into account:

- What types of pipelines/networks occur at which pressure levels. Pipelines made of plastic materials are sometimes susceptible to permeation/ingress. By setting the threshold pressure x above the point where such pipelines occur, reverse flow towards higher-pressure networks can no longer take place. This safeguards gas purity in higher regional networks and the national hydrogen network.
- What types of end users occur at which pressure levels. If, for example, there is a threshold pressure below which no production takes place and no *feedstock* end users are connected, this is a suitable threshold pressure where odorization has no significant consequences.

2.3 The choice between Option A and B

The key consideration is developments in the *Energieregeling* with regard to hydrogen odorization. . If it is determined that DSB networks must by definition be odorized, then only Option A remains possible. If flexibility is offered, a choice can be made between A and B, the advantages and disadvantages of which are set out in Tabel 2.

Tabel 2: Advantages and disadvantages of Options A and B.

Option A Advantages	Option B Advantages
By odorising all parts of the DSB network, safety is ensured without additional measures.	No de-odorization is required in the network. This facilitates dynamic feed-in and feed-out between networks, as reported in the literature (Rosenfeldt, 2024).
Can be adopted without major changes to the <i>Energieregeling</i> , as odorization takes place at the network interface, as is the case with natural gas. A hydrogen gas specification could be added to the Regulation.	Because no de-odorization is required, no odorant is wasted and there is an efficiency advantage in the network. This reduces total network costs.
Odorization takes place centrally upon pressure reduction to 16 bar. This is technically easier than odorization at a lower pressure level with a lower flow rate.	Offers tailored solutions (maatwerk) to DSBs, industries, and local authorities. This can strengthen the development of regional networks.
	Contaminated hydrogen (through oxygen permeation, for example) from low-pressure networks will never be fed into clean regional networks and the national hydrogen network.
Disadvantages	Disadvantages
End users who do not want odorant will need to connect to the Hynetwork, or must offtake from the DSB network and de-odorise.	Odorization will take place at the interface between the DSB and local low-pressure networks. Odorization at low pressure is technically challenging.
Producers in local networks will need to odorise, even if the pressure is low or the supply is variable. This is technically challenging.	The odorization obligation will need to be implemented in legislation on the basis of pressure, whereas it is currently based on the network interface.

This option does not offer tailored solutions (maatwerk) for every regional network or industrial cluster.

There must be sufficient technical evidence that not odorising parts of the DSB network above x bar is sufficiently safe.

3 RQ3: What are the current technologies for removing odorants from hydrogen?

De-odorization is the reverse process of odorization: the removal of odorant from hydrogen. In the HyDelta 3.0 report *Overview of basic elements for hydrogen purity standards* (van Essen et al., 2024) an overview was included of available literature on this subject. As no publications were found specifically addressing the de-odorization of hydrogen, it was decided to look instead at the desulphurisation and de-odorization of bio/green gas, as this involves a comparable technique.

In that work it was described how biogas can be freed from sulphur and odorant through adsorption with activated carbon. By treating or impregnating the activated carbon, the adsorption can be made selective for a specific odorant, such as THT. The odorant level can in this way be reduced to below 3 ppm.

This chapter will answer two questions:

1. Is de-odorization of hydrogen technically feasible?
2. What are the economic considerations of de-odorization of hydrogen within the DSB network?

Nothing is currently known about the de-odorization of sulphur-free odorants, although this process is likely comparable to the methods described below. This is partly because the chemical composition of many sulphur-free odorants is not publicly available, or because sulphur-free odorants are relatively new and not yet commercially deployed. Future projects such as the German H₂-odor project are specifically aimed at investigating whether sulphur-free odorants can also be removed from hydrogen.

3.1 Is de-odorization of hydrogen technically feasible?

Option A, as proposed in Section 2.1, proposes a distribution network in which odorization takes place *top-down* at the decoupling between the TSB and the DSB, as is the case in the current natural gas network. In this scenario, in the case of sulphur-containing odorants, purification must take place to the specification established in the proposed EZK specification. This concerns a maximum of 3 ppm sulphur. If the gas has been nominally odorized and the hydrogen in the DSB network is sulphur-free, the amount of sulphur-containing odorant will need to be reduced from 5–6 ppm to less than 3 ppm. This chapter will investigate whether proven techniques exist that can achieve this technically. As this concerns feed-in to the Hynetwork, the pressures at which these processes take place are also considered.

Interviews and literature research indicate that adsorption processes are the most suitable method for de-odorization of gases in general. THT removal by adsorption is a proven technique at multiple pressure regimes and gas flow rates, including atmospheric (Cui et al., 2009; van Essen et al., 2024), 2–8 bar (de Wild et al., 2006), and 10 bar (Cho et al., 2023). However, not all of these processes are continuous, and specific temperature requirements have been established for some.

Materials used for sulphur-removing de-odorization include metal oxides, zeolites, and treated and/or impregnated (activated) carbon (de Wild et al., 2006; Kang et al., 2007; van Essen et al., 2024). The most common process steps are *fixed bed adsorbers (of packed bed)* and *pressure swing adsorption systems*. Fixed bed adsorbers are reaction columns filled with an adsorbent material (often in the form of pellets) through which the gas passes. The length of the column is calculated based on, among other things, the adsorption capacity of the material and the flow rate of the gas. At the end of the column, the gas has transferred a large proportion of its sulphur-containing

components to the adsorbent material. When the material is saturated and can no longer absorb sulphur components, the pellets are replaced with fresh ones.

In *pressure swing adsorption* systems, adsorption takes place under high pressure, and the adsorbent material is regenerated under low pressure. This allows the material to be used over multiple cycles, with high adsorption efficiency. However, energy is required to achieve the pressure swing. In both methods, the process is semi-continuous, as the adsorbent material needs to be replaced or regenerated.

Figuur 9: De-odorization system proposed by DBI-gut (Lubenau, 2022).

An interview with DVGW/EBI made clear that the removal of sulphur-containing odorants from hydrogen by adsorption (PSA or otherwise) is technically feasible, despite only limited literature being available. DBI-gut, a German research institute, proposes, for smaller gas flows where hydrogen losses are costly, an adsorption system without regeneration (Lubenau, 2022) (**Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**). The system consists of two adsorption columns and is designed to be deployed in series (for additional desulphurisation) and in parallel (when one tank is under maintenance). DBI-gut claims that the system is designed for a capacity in which material only needs to be replaced once a year during de-odorization. It is unknown at what flow rate the system is designed, or what the target odorant level is at the outlet of the system. The system proposes zeolite 13X as the adsorption material. 13X is a proven adsorption material for sulphur-containing odorants such as THT (Cho et al., 2023). DVGW indicated in the interview that various adsorption materials are currently being tested with hydrogen de-odorization as the objective. DVGW/EBI also participates in standardisation work on the subject of hydrogen purification upon injection into the high-pressure network, specifically for DVGW G290 “injection into the high-pressure network, specifically for DVGW G290 “Rückspeicherung von Gasen in vorgelagerte Transportleitungen – Gasbeschaffungsanpassung”.

Based on the above overview, an interview with DVGW/EBI, comparable techniques in biogas/green gas upgrading, and activity in standardisation work, it can be established **that de-odorization of**

hydrogen is technically feasible. The specific process technology (as used in biogas upgrading) is at TRL⁷ 9. The adsorption material is assessed at TRL 6–7.

3.2 What are the economic considerations of de-odorization of hydrogen within the DSB network?

In consultation with the EAG it was noted that an assessment of the expected scale and costs of de-odorization would be useful in the current work and decision-making process surrounding odorization policy. It is difficult to estimate the total volumes of gas that would need to be freed from odorant in a future network, as the distribution network is not yet under development. However, it is possible to make the best possible estimate of the CAPEX/OPEX for odour removal as a function of capacity (in m³(n) of odorized gas/hour). For reference, a typical gas flow at a green gas installation may be around 200 m³(n)/hour.

Although CAPEX estimates for hydrogen odour removal are not available, an analogy can be drawn by looking at the costs of fixed bed or pressure swing absorbers in biogas/CO₂ upgrading/desulphurisation. Both systems are generally suitable for flows of 10 to 10,000 m³(n)/hour (Danish Technological Institute, 2014). OPEX depends on the choice of adsorption material and the capacity for adsorption and regeneration of that material. OPEX is also determined by the maintenance interval, the costs for removing and processing saturated adsorption material, and energy costs.

Figuur 10: CAPEX by capacity for PSA systems (Air Liquide, 2022; Ganesan et al., 2025; Kohlheb et al., 2021; Lubenau, 2022; Urban et al., 2009).

For PSA systems, data on CAPEX at various gas flow rates is available in the public literature. Because the estimates vary and are subject to the conversion of dollars to euros over time and inflation, all data is presented in Figuur 10. As can be seen in the figure, there are considerable capital costs for PSA systems, which scale by approximately €1M extra per 1,000 m³(n)/hour.³

For *fixed-bed* adsorption, DBI estimates that purifying odorant from hydrogen requires a variable CAPEX of 0.115 €/kg (0.0082 €/ m³ (n)) and a fixed CAPEX of €303,000. As can be seen in Figuur

⁷ Technological readiness level. 9 = fully developed and ready for the market.

10Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden. (data point from DBI), the CAPEX for *fixed-bed* adsorption is significantly lower than that for PSA systems. This is in line with expectations, as more complex technology is required for PSA. The calculation in the DBI report showed no clear economy of scale for this type of adsorption system, however (Lubenau, 2022).

The specific adsorption material most suitable for odorant adsorption in hydrogen is still under development, as indicated by DVGW. However, the costs of the adsorption material can be estimated. If it is assumed that zeolite 13X is used, as proposed by DBI, a cost estimate for the adsorption material can be made based on the adsorption capacity.

Zeolite can be used in both PSA and fixed bed systems. Fresh 13X has a reported adsorption capacity for sulphur of up to 179 mg S/g, three times higher than activated carbon (Yang et al., 2018). When these results are calculated specifically for THT, the adsorption capacity is reported as 66 mg THT/g (0.7–0.8 mmol/g) (Cho et al., 2023). Therefore, if 10,000 m³(n) at 18 mg/m³(n) were to be de-odorized, 180,000 mg of THT could be removed by 2,727 kg of zeolite 13X.³

To give some context: 2,727 kg of zeolite is approximately 700 kg/m³, so this would be approximately 4 litres of zeolite. At approximately €4/kg, this would cost €0.012 per kilogram of de-odorized hydrogen. This is under ideal conditions, however. The adsorption capacity of 13X decreases considerably after each regeneration cycle, and the 66 mg THT/g 13X breakthrough adsorption capacity figure is a theoretical number reported in a laboratory setting. Therefore, costs of approximately €0.02–0.03/kg H₂ are more realistic.

However, no publicly available costs yet exist for an adsorption material specifically for odorant - sulphur-free or sulphur-containing - in hydrogen. Only once the specific material, the odorant to be removed, the odorization level, and the gas flow rate are known can an accurate estimate be made of the operational costs, including maintenance, adsorption material processing, and energy costs.

4 RQ4: Is not odorising, or the use of sulphur-free odorants, a feasible and sustainable solution?

4.1 Not odorising

HyDelta 1 described in detail the risks of not odorising hydrogen and the selection of sulphur-free odorants. The conclusion of WPD2.4 was that not odorising distribution networks would increase the safety risk by a factor of 50. However, WPD2.4 states (E. Polman, 2022):

“The distribution of gas is defined as the assembly of pipes and installations under an overpressure of 8 bar or less from the gas receiving station to the gas meter.”

This means that odorization is recommended above 8 bars in that report, which means that both Option A and B remain in line with earlier HyDelta work, as the threshold pressure x in Option B can be set at 8 bar or higher. However, it is not plausible that pipelines within residential areas will be unodorized for safety reasons. Leaving the entire network unodorized is therefore not a feasible solution.

It is conceivable, however, that above 8 bar - for steel pipelines in, for example, port areas, industrial parks, or other relatively sparsely populated zones - unodorized gas could be distributed on the basis of end-user demand. For these unodorized sections, the increased safety risks and the control measures required will need to be assessed. As described above, Option B provides scope for this through tailored solutions (*maatwerk*) per connected regional network/industrial cluster.

HyDelta 4 work package D1C draws a comparable conclusion. In paragraph 6.4.1 of that report, it is concluded that odorization of industrial networks of intermediate pressure is undesirable due to end-user requirements. This work package describes operational and incident-related control measures that contribute to the safety of unodorized intermediate-pressure hydrogen networks. These recommendations can be used as a basis for the above-mentioned requirement for *maatwerk*.

4.2 Odorising with a sulphur-free odorant

In HyDelta 1.0 (Polman E. & Vlap, 2022) and other HyDelta work packages, research has been conducted into which sulphur-free odorants are suitable for the hydrogen network. At present there are several sulphur-free odorants, such as 2- or 1-hexyne, as well as commercial products such as Gasodor-S-Free and Scentinel, that meet the odour, stability, and transport requirements.

The aim of using a sulphur-free odorant is to avoid negatively affecting end users. As discussed above, sulphur-containing odorants such as THT and mercaptans affect fuel cells and industrial catalysts. Research in 2022 showed that 2-hexyne does not affect fuel cells (Vlap et al., 2022). However, it is not expected that many fuel cells will be connected to the nascent hydrogen network. The main off-takers here will primarily be feedstock processes and combustion processes. **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** shows which end users can and cannot be supplied via the network against which odorants.

Figuur 11: Overview of hydrogen end users and where which odorants can be used, based on currently publicly available information.

As shown in Figuur 11 **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**, there is still uncertainty about the use of sulphur-free odorants in industrial processes, where high expected demand exists. No problems are expected with odorants in combustion processes, as ppm-level contaminants have negligible effect on flue gas composition, combustion temperature, flame speed, etc. Sulphur-free odorants have been tested for fuel cells, but these are expected to be supplied by new, clean pipelines specifically for a filling station or by tube trailers.

Another question is whether Hynetwork permits sulphur-free odorants in its network. The EZK specification includes a limit on sulphur components (<3 ppm), but no limits on sulphur-free odorants. The EZK specification does include a requirement concerning ‘other impurities’. This requirement states that the gas:

“Shall not contain solid, liquid or gaseous material that might interfere with the integrity or operation of pipes or any gas appliance”.

Strictly speaking, trace components at ppm level that are proven to have no effect on Hynetwork pipelines or end users of the national hydrogen network would therefore be permitted. However, it can also be interpreted that Hynetwork, as they themselves state, supplies unodorized hydrogen, meaning that the gas supplied must contain no odour, and hence no sulphur-free odorants either. In addition, Hynetwork will also be expected to supply to other countries and the hydrogen delivered will also need to comply with those respective nation’s international requirements and standards.

If a sulphur-free odorant is proven to have no effect on end users such as the process industry, and if Hynetwork accepts sulphur-free odorants, then Option A as shown in Figuur 6 also becomes an option. De-odorization is then no longer required, as no end user of the DSB network - factories, households, or Hynetwork - is affected by the sulphur-free odorant. However, before this could be possible, the following steps would need to be taken:

- Inventory of the catalysts of industries connected to the Hynetwork and DSB network.
- Research into the effects of sulphur-free odorants on, among other things:
 - Fuel production processes
 - Fertiliser and ammonia production
 - Refining
 - Hydrogenation processes in the food industry
- Enquiry to Hynetwork regarding sulphur-free odorants in their system.

- Research into the odorization requirements in the transmission networks of neighbouring countries, e.g. Belgium and Germany, and also at European level.

If the investigations show that there are no problems with the sulphur-free odorant, there is a possibility that Option A aligns well – or better than B - with the needs of network operators and end users.

5 Conclusions and recommendations

The answers to the research questions are summarised below:

RQ1: What are the differences between the hydrogen network and the natural gas network with regard to odorization?

The natural gas network is built top-down. Odorant injection can therefore take place centrally high upstream in the system. There is little to no gas produced decentrally – besides renewable natural gas - at low pressure that is brought all the way back to the HTL. End use of the gas is primarily combustion-based.

In the hydrogen network, the expectation is that the system will be built *bottom-up*. Hydrogen production can occur both centrally and decentrally, including at locations further from transmission pipelines. The initial system will be a connection between clusters and local networks. End use of the gas is primarily as feedstock and for combustion.

RQ2: Where is the best location for odorant injection in the network?

The location where odorization must take place is highly dependent on two factors: the future legislation on odorization (not yet established for hydrogen in the *Energieregeling*) in hydrogen networks, and the form the development of the network takes. Based on how these two aspects develop, the following options can be chosen:

- A. Odorizing the entire DSB network. This means that all end users who wish to receive hydrogen below 30 bar, and who are not connected to the HTL, will receive odorized hydrogen.
- B. A part of the DSB network. Below a legally defined threshold pressure of x bar (for example, 8 bar), all infrastructure is odorized. Above this pressure, odorization is optional and bespoke arrangements (*maatwerk*) are provided with regard to leak detection. The choice of whether or not to odorise depends on customer need, the volume of production, and local external safety considerations. All infrastructure below the threshold pressure is *downstream*, and boosting is no longer possible below the threshold pressure.

With Option A, end users who do not want odorant are expected to nonetheless receive odorized gas. Hynetwork (HTL) also does not want to supply odorized gas, so de-odorization will need to take place during boosting to the TSB. Odorization will also need to take place at feed-in points in the DSB network. For variable or small feed-in flows, such as from electrolysis at a wind farm, odorization is technically challenging.

With Option B, the odorant obligation will need to be defined on the basis of pressure rather than the network interface. The threshold pressure x will need to be carefully determined. Evidence will also need to be provided that not odorising gas distribution networks from $x-16$ bar is safe.⁸ Further research is therefore needed into the specific control measures for unodorized distribution networks.

A major advantage of this option is the complete absence of any need for de-odorization systems; odorant does not need to be removed anywhere in the system. This option also better aligns with the process industry's need to receive unodorized gas ('*maatwerk*'). Option B offers greater flexibility for varying needs per region, and more freedom for network operators to meet customer demand and the expectations of local authorities.

⁸ See HyDelta D1c.1 who investigated safety standards for hydrogen grids, including odorization.

RQ3: What are the current technologies for removing (de-odorising) odorants from hydrogen?

Adsorption techniques are the most common techniques for removing odorants from gases. Examples available on the market include *fixed bed (packed column)* processes and *pressure-swing adsorption* processes (PSA). The process technologies for purifying hydrogen from odorants are assessed as being at TRL 9. The adsorption material for the selective removal of odorants (sulphur-containing and sulphur-free) from hydrogen is assessed at TRL 6–8.

An estimate has been made of the CAPEX for sulphur removal at gas flows of varying flow rates. PSA is more expensive than *fixed-bed* adsorption in CAPEX, but is more commonly used for larger gas flows.

Little could be said about OPEX from an economic perspective, as the appropriate adsorption material is still under development. A rough estimate has been made of the adsorption material costs.

RQ4: Is the use of sulphur-free odorants, or the option of not odorising at all, a feasible and sustainable solution?

Previous HyDelta work packages have concluded that not odorising below 8 bar could increase safety risks. However, for gas networks above 8 bar there is a possibility that it may be safe in some locations, and HyDelta 4.0 work package D1C recommends in subsection 6.4.1 not odorising industrial networks of intermediate pressure for the benefit of end users. This work package proposes operational and incident-related control measures that safeguard safety in unodorized hydrogen networks.

Sulphur-free odorants must align with the needs of hydrogen end users. This means they will need to be tested for interaction with industrial catalysts. Testing has been conducted for interaction with fuel cells (platinum), but this group of end users is expected to be minimal, as they will be supplied by tube trailers or specially designed networks. It will also need to be investigated whether the introduction of sulphur-free odorants into the national hydrogen network is permitted by Hynetwork, in consultation with Hynetwork, and considering the needs of end users of the national hydrogen network and the requirements of neighbouring countries.

If a sulphur-free odorant exists that meets all requirements following the above investigations, then Option A, as described in the report, would be a suitable option for odorization policy.

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